

U. PORTO

ICBAS | INSTITUTO DE CIÊNCIAS
BIOMÉDICAS ABEL SALAZAR
**SCHOOL OF MEDICINE AND
BIOMEDICAL SCIENCES**

Protocol for Conducting Systematic and Automated Aerial Surveys of Intertidal Communities Using Low-Cost Drones

João R. Nunes^{1,2}, Rita da Silva¹, Rocío Nieto-Vilela¹, Cátia Monteiro^{1,2}, Rui Seabra¹ & Fernando P. Lima^{1,2}

1. CIBIO, Centro de Investigação em Biodiversidade e Recursos Genéticos, InBIO Laboratório Associado, Universidade do Porto, Campus de Vairão, 4485-661 Vairão, Portugal BIOPOLIS.
2. ICBAS - School of Medicine and Biomedical Sciences, University of Porto, 4050-313 Porto, Portugal.

1. State-of-the-art

The growing need to understand the key implications of climate change involves measuring biodiversity and understanding community structure and function. Regular biodiversity assessments, however, often pose significant challenges. This is especially true for intertidal communities, which, given the strong habitat variability, complexity, and temporal dynamics (Tomanek & Helmuth, 2002; Glasby et al., 2017), require frequent and comprehensive surveys to obtain meaningful information. Traditional methodologies often lack the necessary spatial extension or taxonomic resolution, are time-consuming, and involve substantial costs (Murfit et al., 2017). Therefore, developing innovative, time- and cost-effective survey methodologies has become a pressing challenge. Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS), commonly known as drones, offer great promise for surpassing some of these limitations (Watts et al., 2012; Anderson & Gaston, 2013; Gonçalves & Henriques, 2015). Their application in scientific research is growing extensively worldwide due to their ability to survey large areas while obtaining meaningful, high-resolution data (Andriolo et al., 2023). Nonetheless, drone-assisted surveys still face some challenges, such as relatively high equipment costs, issues with repeatability, dependence on favorable weather, and legal authorization requirements. Having these challenges in mind, we developed a standardized and accessible drone-based protocol that can be implemented by researchers and adapted for citizen science initiatives, enabling systematic, repeatable, and cost-effective monitoring of intertidal communities.

2. Objectives

The primary objective of this protocol is to establish a standardized and reproducible methodology for the automated photogrammetric surveying of intertidal communities using low-cost, consumer-grade drones. This work focuses on the development, optimization, and implementation of flight missions across multiple intertidal sites, enabling the systematic acquisition of temporal data over extended monitoring periods. More specifically, this protocol seeks to:

- Demonstrate the capability of consumer-grade drones to achieve high spatial resolution (average Ground Sample Distance (GSD) of 0.145 cm/pixel for this specific configuration) suitable for ecological monitoring.
- Assess the effectiveness and efficiency of low-cost drones in capturing reliable datasets for the study of intertidal ecosystems.
- Provide a framework that facilitates large-scale data acquisition and subsequent analysis through open-source tools, thereby reducing the time and resources typically required in ecological research.

Overall, this protocol aims to expand the accessibility of advanced monitoring techniques by offering an affordable and scalable approach to the systematic study of intertidal communities.

3. Equipment and Materials.

- UAS: drone + remote controller
- GPS device
- Computer
- Drone Flight Control Software

Low-cost drone selection

When conducting automated flights for surveying intertidal communities, selecting a low-cost drone with suitable features is essential. The selected drone should support an available Software Development Kit (SDK) (Saito & Mase, 2013) to enable the integration of third-party apps, allowing for custom flight planning and data collection. Among the most cost-effective options (< € 800) are the DJI Mini Series (including the DJI Mini SE, DJI Mini 2, DJI Mini 3, and DJI Mini 3 Pro) and the DJI Air 2. Each one of these models offers distinct features and capabilities that may impact survey outcomes:

1. **Camera Quality:** Different drones come equipped with varying camera specifications, including resolution, lens type, and stabilization features. Higher-resolution cameras are preferable for capturing detailed images of intertidal communities, aiding in accurate species identification and habitat assessment. Gimbal mechanisms are also fundamental in ensuring correct angles when conducting aerial missions.
2. **Flight Time:** Battery capacity is a critical factor, particularly when surveying larger areas. Drones with longer flight times can cover more ground per flight, reducing the need for frequent battery changes and enhancing data collection efficiency, but are also heavier and expensive.
3. **Weight and Portability:** The size and weight of the drone influence how easy it is to transport and deploy in field settings. Lightweight drones are generally more convenient for researchers working in remote intertidal areas and can be launched easily by hand. Additionally, lighter drones (<250 g) have fewer legal requirements than heavier ones.
4. **Limitations and Capabilities:** Each drone has specific limitations, such as maximum wind resistance, altitude restrictions, speed, etc. Mini drones are more susceptible to weather conditions, which can limit flights under certain circumstances.

The drone selected for the testing and optimization of the protocol described herein was the DJI Mini 3 Pro. This foldable and compact drone (24 cm wide, with a height of 7 cm) weighs only 249 g, placing it within the lowest flight category under Portuguese aviation regulations. Recent firmware updates have enabled the integration of Software Development Kits (SDKs), thereby expanding its compatibility with third-party applications capable of controlling flight operations. The drone is equipped with a 1/1.3-inch CMOS sensor that captures images at 48 MP resolution (8064 × 6048 pixels) with a 24 mm focal length. Additionally, it includes an automated trigger function that allows images to be captured immediately upon arrival at pre-defined waypoints, facilitating systematic and repeatable data acquisition while reducing user bias. Although the DJI Mini 3 Pro is no longer in production or available for sale through official markets, its successor, the [DJI Mini 4 Pro](#), retains equivalent features and functionality, making it a reliable and accessible alternative for applying this protocol.

Figure 1. a) DJI Mini 3 Pro in unfolded configuration with propellers attached, ready for deployment. b) DJI Mini 3 Pro in folded configuration, illustrating its portability and suitability for fieldwork due to its compact design and ease of transport.

GPS device

To conduct effective surveys of limited areas within intertidal rocky shores using automated drone flights, it is essential to obtain accurate georeferenced coordinates for flight planning. For this purpose, a precision GPS unit capable of sub-meter accuracy (<50 cm) is recommended. In this study, a SparkFun RTK Facet L-Band® ([SparkFun](#)) was employed to record the central coordinates of each quadrat, achieving a precision of approximately 3 cm. To optimize field efficiency, the eight additional surrounding points required per quadrat were subsequently calculated in RStudio, thereby reducing the need for extensive on-site measurements (Figure 2b). The resulting coordinate sets were then imported into the drone flight software to enable the execution of automated survey missions.

Figure 2. a) Distribution of GPS points; b) Schematic representation of coordinate generation in RStudio. The red point indicates the central coordinate measured in the field using a high-precision GPS, while the surrounding black points represent additional coordinates calculated through an RStudio script.

Drone Flight Control Software: Setting up the Flights

Automated aerial surveys require careful pre-planning of flight paths using specialized drone flight control software. These applications, enabled through the drone's Software Development Kit (SDK), allow the user to define and automate various aspects of the mission, including trajectory, altitude, image capture, image overlap, and survey coverage. The primary advantage of employing such software lies in its ability to standardize and automate flight operations, thereby ensuring consistent data collection and minimizing manual intervention. This is particularly important for repetitive monitoring efforts, such as the monthly intertidal surveys tested here.

Several flight control platforms are currently available, including [DJI Ground Station Pro](#), [DroneDeploy](#), [DroneLink](#), and [Pix4D](#), among others. All provide functionalities to program flight paths, optimize survey coverage, and automate image acquisition. The choice of software should be guided by the requirements of the study, such as survey area size, resolution needs, and compatibility with the drone model.

For this protocol, [DroneLink](#) was selected due to its accessibility, user-friendly interface, and flexibility, making it well-suited for the systematic and repeatable monitoring of intertidal environments. Flight parameters were adjusted to optimize data collection according to the study's objectives:

- **Altitude:** Flights were conducted at 5–10 m above ground level to obtain high-resolution imagery while maintaining adequate coverage of each quadrat.
- **Gimbal Orientation:** The camera was set to -90° (nadiral position), ensuring a perpendicular angle to the ground and minimizing image distortion.
- **Speed:** Adjusted according to local environmental conditions to ensure image stability, reduce motion distortion, and optimize mission duration.

The adjustment of these parameters ensured the systematic and consistent acquisition of imagery, providing a reliable basis for accurate temporal analyses and comparisons.

Figure 3. Planning of the drone missions using DroneLink. a) Software interface for programming survey missions. b) Representation of the predefined flight pattern above a previously selected quadrat. c) Example of a planned mission with georeferenced aerial photographs displayed in the mobile application.

4. Post-Flight Data processing

Following data collection, the acquired images were processed to generate orthomosaics. This step required specialized photogrammetric software capable of stitching together individual aerial images into a georeferenced representation of the study area. The orthomosaic generation process involves correcting geometric distortions, aligning overlapping images, and balancing color values to ensure an accurate and consistent depiction of the region of interest. For this protocol, [WebODM](#), an open-source photogrammetry platform, was employed as the main processing tool. WebODM was selected for its capacity to handle large datasets efficiently while maintaining a high level of accuracy in the resulting products.

To optimize the quality of the orthomosaics, the processing workflow was refined through multiple tests, and the following parameter configuration was adopted:

- **auto-boundary:** true
- **crop:** 0
- **dem-resolution:** 0.5
- **feature-quality:** ultra
- **ignore-GSD:** true
- **orthophoto-resolution:** 0.5
- **pc-quality:** ultra

Figure 4. Processing of images from a quadrat at Mindelo using WebODM. a) 3D reconstruction generated from the original drone photographs. b) Sequence of aerial images captured over the quadrat. c) Quadrat location on a satellite map, illustrating the enhanced resolution and exposure of the area of interest compared to Google Maps®. d) Final orthomosaic produced by WebODM, ready for cropping and analysis.

For the processing phase, the nine images collected for each quadrat were uploaded to the photogrammetry software, with processing options configured to align with the study objectives. It should be noted that generating higher-quality outputs increases both processing time and computational requirements.

Figure 5. Data processing setup using WebODM. a) Creation of a new project. b) Upload the photos, set the parameters previously mentioned, and initiate the creation of orthomosaics.

After processing, the resulting orthomosaics for each quadrat were downloaded and stored for subsequent analysis. Due to potential deviations in the drone's positioning, particularly in repeated monthly or temporal surveys, additional adjustments and cropping might be necessary to ensure that each orthomosaic consistently represented the same area of interest. Once standardized, the datasets are ready for the subsequent analysis. Repeating this process across different months enables the assessment of species distribution and abundance, habitat structure, and temporal ecological changes in these dynamic intertidal environments, while also providing a clear visual representation of these changes.

5. Survey Methodology: Step-by-step procedure

Site Selection and Flight Planning

- Select suitable intertidal sites for aerial surveys.
- Record the central coordinates of each quadrat using a high-precision GPS device.
- Calculate the coordinates of the eight surrounding points using an R script or other computational method.
- Program the survey missions in flight control software using the pre-collected coordinates.
- Set flight parameters, including altitude based on area size and desired resolution, and gimbal orientation to -90° to capture perpendicular images.
- Ensure sufficient image overlap (approximately 70%) for effective photogrammetric analysis.

Pre-Flight Preparation

- Check weather conditions and tide schedules, and plan survey dates and months for data collection.
- Ensure all equipment is fully charged and operational.
- Conduct a pre-flight inspection of the drone.

Data Collection

- Launch the drone at each site and execute the pre-planned automated flight path.
- Configure the drone to capture images of the intertidal zone upon arrival at each coordinate.
- Program the drone to return to its home location after completing image acquisition.

Post-Flight Processing

- Download and organize the collected data.
- Upload the images to photogrammetry software to create 3D models and orthomosaics.
- Conduct data analysis, including species identification and abundance estimation, using manual annotation and/or automated classifiers.

6. Conclusion

The application of this protocol enabled the generation of high-resolution orthomosaics, providing detailed visual records of intertidal regions and supporting accurate analyses of spatial and temporal changes within the study areas. The standardized and repeatable drone surveys allowed the detection of fine-scale variations in substrate composition, algae cover, and the distribution of intertidal organisms.

This approach facilitates the identification of seasonal patterns and potential long-term ecological trends, offering new insights into the dynamics of these complex ecosystems. Multiple orthomosaics can be produced for each quadrat across different sites and arranged side by side to illustrate temporal variations throughout the year (Figure 6). Furthermore, the creation of time-lapse visualizations in video/GIF format enables a clear and intuitive representation of community dynamics over time, enhancing both scientific interpretation and communication of results.

Figure 6. Final orthomosaic outputs for seven months of data collection across three tidal levels in Mindelo, Portugal: (a) Top, (b) Mid, and (c) Low. These mosaics illustrate temporal variations in intertidal communities over the study period.

Figure 7. Highlights of field work and aerial survey missions demonstrating methodology and site conditions across the year.

Figure 8. Comparison of spatial coverage and level of detail between survey methods. (a) Orthomosaic (11 × 11 m) generated from drone flights. (b) Photoquadrat (0.25 × 0.25 m) taken at ground level. (c) Zoomed-in section of the drone orthomosaic corresponding to the quadrat area.

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# Protocol for Conducting Systematic and Automated Aerial Surveys of Intertidal
Communities Using Low-Cost Drones: Generate Sampling Coordinates
# Author: João Ramalho Nunes
# Date: 2025-03-02

#Libraries
library(geosphere)
library(readxl)
library(dplyr)

#User Settings
input_file <- "input_coordinates.xlsx"
output_file <- "output_coordinates.csv"
distance <- 3.5

#Load GPS Coordinates
points <- read_excel(input_file) %>%
  mutate(lon = as.numeric(lon),
         lat = as.numeric(lat))

#Define Orientation & Distances (center + 8 surrounding coordinates)
directions <- c(360, 45, 90, 135, 180, 225, 270, 315)
distances <- ifelse(directions %% 90 == 0, distance, sqrt(2) * distance)

#Generate Surrounding Coordinates
make_points <- function(lon, lat, id) {
  center <- data.frame(center_id = id, point_number = 1,
                      type = "Center", lon = lon, lat = lat)

  surroundings <- lapply(seq_along(directions), function(i) {
    xy <- destPoint(c(lon, lat), b = directions[i], d = distances[i])
    data.frame(center_id = id,
              point_number = i + 1,
              type = "Surrounding",
              lon = xy[1], lat = xy[2])
  }) %>% bind_rows()

  bind_rows(center, surroundings)
}

#Apply to All GPS Coordinates
output <- bind_rows(mapply(make_points, points$lon, points$lat,
                          id = seq_len(nrow(points)), SIMPLIFY = FALSE))

#Save
write.csv(output, output_file, row.names = FALSE)

```

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